

FABRICATION OF IN SITU PARTICULATE COMPOSITE BY INJECTING N₂ GAS INTO MOLTEN ALUMINUM

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Abstract

Nitrogen-hydrogen mixed gas was injected into molten aluminum to produce in situ particle/Al alloy composite. All in situ particles were incorporated in the matrix on condition that lithium was added. Part of the in situ particles were incorporated into Al-5%Ti alloy, although they were eliminated from molten pure aluminum and Al-4.5%Zr alloy. A volume fraction of the in situ nitride particles was calculated by measuring the weight gain of the total system, and the volume fraction was reached to 20% when the gas injection was conducted into Al-5%Ti-1%Li alloy for 60 minutes at 1273K. The ultimate tensile strength of the gas injected Al-5%Ti-10%Mg alloy and was 370MPa.

KEYWORDS: Aluminum matrix composite; In situ reaction; Nitride particles; Gas injection.

1. Introduction

In general, aluminum matrix composites strengthened by a various kinds of ceramics particles have high elastic modulus, excellent wear resistance and high-temperature strength. Since a particulate composite can be manufactured through a casting rout, an application of metal matrix composites(MMCs) to a large construction material can be expected. But there are also some problems which is still difficult to overcome by a conventional manufacturing process. Difficulties in incorporating small particles into molten aluminum and

preventing the interfacial reaction are the typical examples of such a kind of problem. But with the help of the in situ reaction, which utilizes the internal reaction to synthesize the strengthening particle, we can expect a dispersion of small particles and even a high volume fraction. In this paper, nitrogen-gas injection into molten aluminum or aluminum alloy and a following formation of nitride particles are dealt with for the purpose of developing a new manufacturing process. The advantages of this process are (1) a simplicity and (2) a feasibility to achieve at a high volume fraction of particles. The formation of in situ particles was evaluated by observing a microstructure and calculating a volume fraction of in situ particles. Some specimens were submitted to a tensile test for measuring the ultimate tensile strength.

2. Experimental Procedure

2.1. Fabrication process and the observation of the microstructure

The flow chart of this experiment is shown in Fig.1. The matrix alloy used in this experiment was melted in a nitrogen atmosphere by an induction heating and then held at 1273K. N_2 -10% H_2 mixed gas was used to reduce the oxygen pressure in N_2 gas. Platinum asbestos was used to act as a catalyst to convert oxygen with hydrogen into H_2O . Then H_2O was absorbed in silica gel and the mixed gas with lower oxygen pressure was injected into molten aluminum for 60min. The flow rate of the injection gas was 200cc/min.

Figure 1. Flow chart of the experimental procedure

2.2. Measurement of the effect of alloying elements and the weight gain

Titanium, zirconium and lithium were used as alloying elements in this experiment because the free energy of nitride formation of these elements are low enough to be formed⁽¹⁾. N₂-H₂ mixed gas was injected into molten aluminum, Al-5.0wt%Ti, Al-4.5wt%Zr and Al-5.0wt%Li for 60min. After the specimen was solidified, it was sectioned and polished to serve a microscopic observation. The cross section of the specimen was observed by scanning electron microscope(SEM) and analyzed by energy probe micro analyzer(EPMA). Volume fraction of the in situ particles was calculated from a weight gain of the specimen. Total weight of crucible, starting matrix alloy and injection rod was measured before the experiment(w1) and the total weight was measured again after the gas injection(w2). The weight gain (Δw) was obtained by substituting W1 from W2. The weight gain was corrected by adding a weight of the vaporized aluminum which was obtained by injecting argon gas and measuring the weight loss caused by a vaporization.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Effects of alloying elements on dispersion behavior of in situ particles

Mechanical properties of particulate composite is directly affected by the volume fraction and the distribution of the reinforcements. So the dispersion behavior of the in situ particles were investigated for pure Al, Al-Ti, Al-Zr and Al-Li systems. In case pure aluminum and Al-Zr alloy were used as the starting matrix, no in situ particles were observed in the matrix because they were eliminated from molten aluminum and Al-Zr alloy. On the other hand, in case that titanium or lithium was added to molten aluminum, in situ particles were incorporated into molten phase; however, some amount of in situ particles were still eliminated from Al-Ti alloy.

3.2. Microstructure of the gas injected Al-Ti matrix composite

Fig.2 shows a scanning electron micrograph and X-ray images of gas injected Al-5wt%Ti specimen. According to Fig.2, we can see some overlaps between titanium image and nitrogen image where white particles exist in the scanning electron micrograph. The overlaps between aluminum and nitrogen image also indicates the formation of aluminum nitride. From these results, two reactions shown below are considered to occur in this system.

Although both titanium and aluminum were converted into nitrides by injecting N_2-H_2 mixed gas, the quantity of titanium nitride was less than that of aluminum nitride because of the composition of the matrix(Al:95%,Ti:5%). But there were still some particles which were eliminated and were not incorporated in this system.

Figure 2. Scanning electron micrograph and X-ray images of Al, Ti and N of N_2-H_2 gas injected Al-5wt%Ti alloy. (Temperature; 1273K, Injection time; 60min.)

3.3. Quantitative estimation of formation of in situ nitride particles

As described in the former section, it became apparent that nitride particles were formed by injecting nitrogen gas into molten aluminum alloy. But nitride particles were incorporated into the liquid phase only in case of titanium and lithium alloying, whereas nitride particles were eliminated from pure aluminum matrix and Al-Zr alloy matrix. Wettability between the liquid phase and the in situ nitride particles is considered to affect this phenomenon. If an in situ particle formed at the interface between nitrogen gas and the molten aluminum alloy shows a good wettability with the liquid phase then the particle can be incorporated, but if it shows a poor wettability then it would surface with the bubble. Only Al-Li matrix system among the four systems presented the complete incorporation of the in situ particles. Lithium alloying is reported to decrease the surface energy of molten aluminum⁽²⁾ and also improve the wettability with ceramics⁽³⁾ and carbon⁽⁴⁾, hence, it became possible to incorporate in situ particles. Since only minute amounts of lithium alloying can reduce the surface energy of aluminum⁽²⁾, we expected 1% lithium alloying with Al-Ti alloy would make it possible to incorporate in situ particles into the molten phase without a degradation of the matrix properties.

Fig.3 shows a weight gain of Al-5wt%Ti alloy and Al-5wt%Ti-1wt%Li alloy by N₂-H₂ mixed gas injection and following formation of in-situ particles. According to Fig.3, the weight gain of Al-Ti-Li alloy was slightly higher than that of Al-Ti alloy, and furthermore, every in situ particle was incorporated in case of lithium containing system. For example, the weight gain of lithium containing system with 60-minute injection was 10%, which equals to 18% and 21% in volume fraction assuming that all nitrogen turned to aluminum nitride and titanium nitride, respectively. As it can be seen in Fig.4, sufficient dispersion (about 20% in volume fraction) of in situ particles was observed.

3.4. Tensile strength of the in situ nitride/Al-Ti-Mg alloy composite

In this section, ultimate tensile strength of the gas injected Al-Ti-Mg alloy is described. Magnesium was considered to have the same effect as lithium on the dispersion behavior of in situ nitride particles. Fig.5 shows the ultimate tensile strength of the Al-5wt%Ti-10wt%Mg alloy which was melted at 1273K for 1 hour in Ar atmosphere (comparison material) and that of the N₂ gas injected alloy (nitride composite). As clearly seen in Fig.5, ultimate tensile strength of the gas injected specimen was nearly 3.5 times as high as that of the comparison material so that an improvement of tensile strength by dispersing nitride particles was confirmed.

Figure 3. The weight gain of Al-5wt%Ti and Al-5wt%Ti-1%Li alloy

Figure 4. Scanning electron micrograph of gas injected Al-5wt%Ti-1wt%Li alloy

Figure 5. Ultimate tensile strength of N₂-H₂ gas injected specimen and the comparison material

4. Conclusions

N₂-H₂ mixed gas was injected into molten aluminum to synthesize the in situ nitride composite and following results were obtained.

1. In situ nitride particles were incorporated and dispersed partially in molten Al-5wt%Ti and completely in molten Al-5wt%Li alloy although they were eliminated from molten pure aluminum and Al-4.5wt%Zr alloy.
2. According to a measurement of the weight gain for Al-5wt%Ti and Al-5wt%Ti-1wt%Li system, the volume fraction of the in situ particles were about 20% with a 60-minute injection.
3. The U.T.S. of the gas injected Al-5wt%Ti-10wt%Mg alloy was 370MPa which was about 3.5 times as high as that of the comparison material.

5. References

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